

SMART LIBRARIES: ENHANCING THE LIBRARY EXPERIENCE

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ABSTRACT

Modern libraries are being redefined more and more as locations to have unlimited access to knowledge from a variety of sources and in a variety of formats. By offering literature that can be accessed virtually and helping librarians navigate and analyze vast amounts of data using a range of digital resources, they are expanding their services beyond the physical boundaries of a building. Libraries are evolving into community centers where people can participate in lifelong learning. Here, the concept of a smart library evolved, where resources can be accessed easily and with less staff intervention. Smart Library provides state of the art automated infrastructure and sophisticated technologies like automatic gates, lighting, self-service kiosks, mobile library services on the smart phone or handheld devices, offer limitless digital collection via the Internet, provides e-learning facilities & learning spaces; and uses the social media platforms to share information about its collection and service. So the Smart libraries will revolutionize library operations and services. In this paper, we will discuss various concepts, needs, components and services provided by Smart Libraries.

Keywords: Smart Library, Technology, services, infrastructure, mobile library services

SMART LIBRARY: CONCEPT

According to Burgess (2010), the term "Smart Library" is a combination of phrases Smart and Library. It refers to something that is adaptable, adaptive, extensible, responsive, and human-like. A smart library is a system of software and hardware which provides a variety of options for finding and supplying vital knowledge to all users in accordance to needs and requirements of them (Jerkov, Sofronijevic & Stanisic, 2015).

Therefore, the Smart Library is a place to keep knowledge and resources systematically to ensure that users access proper and timely library services. Thus, we can define a smart library as one that is more adaptable to new trends, more flexible in terms of its collection and services, and more extensible in terms of its service hours.

NEED FOR SMART LIBRARIES

In the modern era, smart libraries are essential. They are required in order to maximize user information needs and make the most of library resources through the application of contemporary information technology.

1. Access enhancement to Library services with 24x7x365 days availability of library resources, remote access to different types of resources like e-books, e-journals, and databases subscribed by the library; it also provides state-of-the-art search ability to different types of resources subscribed by the Library via Smart OPAC.
2. User experience is enriched in Smart Library, which provides personalized services with AI-powered systems to offer users, such as book recommendations and suggestions based on their past issue history. Smart Library has the potential to provide an interactive environment by merging technologies like digital displays with VR/ AR devices. RFID technology and self-service kiosks will save users time in finding documents on the shelf, borrowing, and returning documents.

3. **Increased Operational Efficiency with Smart Library:** Smart Library has the potential to provide efficiency to routine activities of library professionals, as technologies will automate the routine tasks like shelf arrangement, sorting of books, and less staff intervention.
4. **Increased Operational Efficiency for Library Staff:** Smart technologies automate the routine tasks, including inventory control, tracking of books, book sorting, reminders, and alerts—automated collection and analysis of user data for identification of most used resources and most used library services. Future decisions can be made on the basis of the inputs. Library space can be optimized with sensors and data analytics technologies.
5. **More Promotion of Digital Literacy:** Smart Libraries will provide access to computers, technologies, tools, and a stable internet connection, which will help in bridging the digital divide. It offers training and workshops to enhance users' digital literacy skills, such as user manuals of subscribed resources, how to use resources, application of software, and future technologies and tools.

So, Smart libraries are the need of the hour. They are needed to achieve maximum satisfaction of the user's information needs and maximum utilization of the library resources via maximum use of the available modern information technology. The report submitted by Ministry of Education, Government of India on New National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) has emphasized the development of a digital Library and resources for education. Smart libraries have the potential of providing resources and services 24x7x365 beyond the physical boundaries of libraries.

SMART LIBRARIES AND THEIR COMPONENTS

A library can be considered a Smart Library if it offers Smart Library Services (such as appropriate infrastructure, embedded artificial intelligence, IT-based services, and social media access) to Smart People (users who are more adaptable, tolerant, creative, empowered, and intelligent) at a Smart Place (built with more environmental concerns in mind, resulting to the concept of Green Libraries) in a Smart Governance Environment (where the working of library and its management is more transparent, collaborative, and more open towards the social and cultural environment).

Figure 1. Smart Library by Schöpfel, 2018

In order to become more effective, user-centered, and relevant in the digital age, libraries can integrate technology in various ways, as shown by Schöpfel's (2018) perspective on smart libraries. It is a dynamic process rather than a set design, necessitating careful evaluation of the advantages and disadvantages of incorporating "smartness" into the library environment.

SMART LIBRARY AND ITS SERVICES

A library should have proper state-of-the-art infrastructure, embedded with AI and IT-based services and tools in promotion of library resources which includes e-resources and databases.

INFRASTRUCTURE OF SMART LIBRARY

Smart Libraries need to have smart infrastructure in place so that they can provide innovative services to their users. Proper infrastructure can improve the library's potential to provide high-quality services and resources to its users. Today's Libraries must have proper IT infrastructure to provide services to their patrons. The infrastructure includes:

Library Automation: Daniels et al. (2019) elaborated that Library automation means reducing human interference in day-to-day library services in order to provide users with the desired information with maximum ease and at the minimum cost. Primarily, Library automation can be classified as all library databases and housekeeping operations of the library. The library can make use of various open-source and proprietary software for automating the library, which can lead to ease of work and save human power and time. Web-OPAC is an added facility that automates the search for library resources online.

Interactive Library Website: The library website acts as a gateway to the library, where it can display and reflect its vision, mission, objectives, collection, services, resources, facilities, etc., to its users. It can act as a bridge between the library and the community. One can get all the information about the library while sitting anywhere. The library website should be dynamic and also interactive. Chatbot can also be installed on the library website.

Digital Libraries: Institutions that offer variety of resources with the help of specialized personnel, to choose, organize, preserve and intellectual access to, and interpret, disseminate, maintain the validity of, and ensure the increase the lifespan of collections of digital works so that they can be quickly accessible to users of specific users are known as digital libraries. (Digital Library Federation, 1998). The main components of a digital library are people, digital resources, and technology. Modern Libraries are purchasing and subscribing to wide variety of e-resources which includes e-books and e-Journals. A library attached to an educational institution may have a prospectus, photographs, pamphlets, and reports in digital format. Digital resources are more in demand as they solve the space problem of the library, they are cost-effective, the content is always up-to-date, and can be made available instantly. Libraries can create their own Digital library to access the available resources of the library.

RFID-based Library Technology: The application of the RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) technology based library services can revolutionize libraries. Every library document is tagged with RFID tags. Then, middleware software is used to connect the present library automation software and RFID hardware, which includes RFID tags, staff stations, security gates, self-check-in kiosks, drop boxes, and handheld devices. RFID technology helps with easy check-in/check-out, stock verification and rectification, and tracking, sorting, or detecting library holdings.

Institutional Repository: Information Repository of a library preserves digital objects and makes available an institution's scholarly and creative output. It is indexed in major Internet

search engines and discoverable by more than just the campus community. It provides access to scholarly articles, which include:

- Presentations,
- Teaching materials,
- Project Reports,
- Open educational resources,
- Textbooks, learning materials
- Institutional reports, documentation
- Departments/offices/programs reports
- Question Papers

Virtual Conferencing and Meeting Systems: A smart library should be equipped with the infrastructure for Virtual Meeting and Conferencing. In order to organize various activities and to inform users about services and collections, libraries can have a virtual meeting setup. Software and hardware for virtual meetings can be used to organize lectures, workshops, reading circles, meetings, talks, and competitions.

Smart Learning Spaces: Modern-day users want libraries not as a sole source for accessing information but as more productive spaces. These days, students want to learn and work anywhere, and they seek out ongoing access to educational resources in a group setting. The constantly available Internet and locations for quiet learning are probably the reasons behind their shifting expectations. Libraries ought to offer spaces for virtual meetings, media productions, active learning, and other activities that encourage teamwork and practical work. In order to encourage students to learn effectively, the space should have cozy furniture, modular furnishings, wireless networks, and electrical outlets on reading tables, multimedia labs, etc.

CCTV: The Maintenance of security in any library is essential. Closed-Circuit TV (CCTV) can be used for surveillance in libraries to safeguard their possession of books and information in every corner of the library. By installing the CCTV cameras in the library, an eye can be kept on the property counter and the shelf area of the library.

Scanning and Printing Service: Smart Library also requires centralized services like scanning and printing for its users. Users should be allowed to scan and print documents from any device (laptop, tablet, or mobile device) or from the computers in the libraries.

QR-based Services: The primary benefit of QR codes is that they can store more data, require a small space for printing, do not require specialized printers, and are easy to scan with a mobile scanner. We can share with the users one simple QR code about Library services, Library Feedback form, Library Registration for e-resources form, library brochure, new-arrivals lists, and Webinar/Conference or Seminar Brochure.

Services for Persons with Disabilities (PwDs): The Census 2001 estimates that 2.1% of India's total population is comprised of 21 million persons with disabilities. The population of such includes persons who have disabilities like cannot see, hear, speak or mental disabilities. So the library keeps a few computers reserved for these users who have Braille resources, DAISY or JAWS Software, and Braille Printers. The trained staff of the library caters to their specific information and service needs with priority.

Federated Search and Remote Access: The main goal of today's libraries is to connect users with the information they seek, for which libraries subscribe to many e-databases and have a massive collection of e-resources. It facilitates a Single Search Box for searching from multiple resources. Remote access is the facility given to a user through which he/ she can access a computer, tablet, or smartphone with an Internet connection from different locations. In this system, the library creates a username and password for the patrons, which will enable them to connect to the library systems and access the electronic resources.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND LIBRARIES

Encyclopedia Britannica states that Artificial intelligence is the capacity of a digital computer or a computer-operated robot to carry out tasks usually related with intelligent entities.

- **Drones:** Libraries can make use of drones in a very smart way. Bigger libraries can use drones to transfer the books from one place to another within the library. This technology is very useful to deliver the books to the library patrons (senior citizens/ Persons with Disabilities) who are primarily in a densely populated city. According to the American Library Association, users may expect drones to be part of library technology resources. They can be used to provide new opportunities for research output.
- **Robots:** Using artificial intelligence approaches, robots are a mechanical tool that either directly under human supervision or a pre-defined program or set of general guidelines, completing automation tasks. (Nowrin, 2016). It can help libraries perform regular activities and sort library material like humans do. Libraries can use Robots for providing library tutorials or to assist them in the locating resource of the Library.
- **3D Printers:** Techopedia.com defines A 3D printer is a kind of material design printer that uses additive manufacturing to create 3D models and products of gadgets and parts. 3D printers are a costly and sophisticated technology. Libraries can provide a 3D printing facility to their patrons in order to deliver opportunities for community engagement and collaboration. The use of these printers requires special training.
- **Makerspaces:** Merriam-Webster dictionary defines Makerspace as A public workshop where makers can work on small personal projects. Makerspaces provide seamless access to tools and resources that are not accessible and affordable for users at home. Ultimately, it helps stakeholders create ideas and creativity, and creates a collaborative, interdisciplinary research environment. In 2010, Lauren Britton introduced the Fab(ulous) Lab at Fayetteville Free Library, New York. Makerspaces provide patrons with an opportunity to acquire knowledge through hands-on exploration. Makerspaces will help libraries build a strong relationship with society and encourage them to be creators of information, not just consumers.
- **Augmented Reality:** Augmented Reality (AR) is a connection between the real and virtual worlds. With AR interaction, an image-based augmented reality application is being developed, allowing users to search for information about the library or the location of the library's resources. Some libraries are even using AR to develop library orientation materials. The application for accessing AR can easily be installed on the user's device. Many libraries use special equipment, such as glasses, to apply AR. Augmented Reality can be seen as a help to the library staff.
- **Chatbots:** Merriam-Webster dictionary defines Chatbots as a virtual assistant meant to interact with people. It is a popular tool in the context of implementing a smart

library. It can act as 24/7 virtual assistance, as a tool for instant retrieval of information, personalization of user recommendations based upon their past interaction, multilingual support, and the power of integration with library catalogue and databases.

- **Social Media Platforms:** The libraries can use these environments to interact with a broader variety of users in innovative ways. These are basically the marketing tools for the libraries to increase library usage, boost new services and resources, and attract library patrons in this age of Information technology. The library can reach out to users to tell them about their collections, the services they provide, and the events they organize by using social media platforms like Blogs, Instagram, Twitter (X), Facebook, YouTube, etc. These platforms can be used for:
 - Sharing information and photos of the upcoming library event
 - Sharing of Library Services
 - Key features of the Library collection
 - Comments and feedback from users
 - User orientation programmes
 - Library Literacy programmes
 - Promotion of library services
 - Library feedback form
 - Ask a Librarian service
 - Link to Library registration of e-resources and databases.

Overall, Social Media aligns with smart libraries as it helps make library services more accessible and interactive.

Electronic Newsletters: These are a way by which people are reminded about events. A library can publish a newsletter showcasing the library's activities, services, and collections. The library can also invite articles from readers about their views and expectations of the library. This tool sometimes acts as a real motivator and encourages various contributors, knowledge leaders, and users to share more and more information. The method to deliver the newsletters can be opted for, with options to choose from, such as receiving email alerts for the activities.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this paper is to discuss various components and services of smart Library services and how libraries have changed their nature in the modern scenario. As the change is always constant so mere adoption of technology is not Smart libraries, leveraging the technology in creation of accessible, efficient and user centered library services which can meet the changing needs of the users in modern digital age. Smart libraries are needed to achieve maximum satisfaction of the user information need, maximum utilization of the library resources via maximum use of the available modern information technology. If a library has proper infrastructure for Information technology application and it is embedded with Artificial Intelligence products, and provides IT based services and uses Social Media for the promotion of its resources and services it can called as a “Smart Library”. These libraries will be able to contribute a lot in the development of “Smart Cities”. Library

professionals should keep themselves updated with modern development in the field and library associations should hold time to time events where the professionals can learn and develop new technologies.

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